

ASSESSMENT OF TEACHING STRATEGIES IN OMAR DISTRICT, MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION, DIVISION-SULU

Liza J. Jumlain and Anang Fatma T. Jawali

Sulu State College, Bangkal, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11177964>

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the teaching strategies for students' engagement and learning as assessed by teachers in Omar district, Sulu on fiscal year 2023. It employed descriptive design with 100 teacher-respondents taken through purposive sampling method. The following are findings of this study: The demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu reveals that they are mostly female, in their early adulthood, single or married, below 10 years in service, and have bachelor's degree. The extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu shows that they have high or very high levels of agreement with the statements related to differentiated instruction, active learning, technological integration, and effective communication. The tables also show that there are less or some variations among the teacher-respondents in their ratings of the teaching strategies. The tables reveal that there are no significant differences in the assessments of the teacher-respondents across the different groups for most of the variables, except for effective communication aspect by age, active learning aspect by civil status, and active learning aspect by length of service. The correlation coefficients between the four sub-categories of teaching strategies: differentiated instruction, active learning, technological integration, and effective communication reveals that all the correlations are positive and significant, meaning that there is a linear relationship between the variables. The table also indicates that the correlations are either moderate or low, meaning that the strength of the relationship is not very high.

Keywords: *Assessment, Assessment of teaching strategies, teaching Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Effective strategies for student engagement and learning are essential because it helps improve academic performance and create a positive learning environment. Enhance motivation cater to diverse learning needs and foster a lifelong love for learning. By continually exploring and implementing these strategies educators can nurture students' intellectual development and pave the way for their future success.

Teaching methods that consider the interaction between students and their instructors have a positive effect on students' learning. The most effective strategy that Instructors use to benefit student's learning in the classroom is to encourage them to link their experience in learning in the past to the new knowledge in the present through the class discussion and help them come up with new ideas that benefit them in their real-life problem-solving (Akpan & Beard, 2016). This strategy can help students build self-confidence and encourage them to broaden their knowledge and facilitate their learning.

According to Poon (2013), using teaching strategies that includes both traditional and technology learning can improve students learning and provoke them to participate actively in the learning process. This approach helps students trust on their capacity and be self-efficacy in learning (Redding & Walberg, 2012). Teaching strategies can also align with the idealism methodology that is based on Socratic dialogue stimulating students' critical thinking. The teacher's role is as a guide for students in the classroom to facilitate their curiosity in learning. The instructor stimulates students by asking leading questions to help them looking for more knowledge (Gutek, 2013; Saritaş, 2016). Thus, the instructor's role is to facilitate the learning procedure for learners to motivate them to have critical thinking, engagement, and independent learning.

Therefore, the researcher assessed the teaching strategies utilized by the teachers in Omar District to shed light on the performance of the students.

Research Questions:

This study determined the teaching strategies for student's engagement and learning in Omar district on fiscal year 2023. Specifically, this research gathered information to answer each of the following questions.

1. What is the socio- demographic profile of the respondents in terms of ;
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Civil status;
 - 1.4 Length of Service; and
 - 1.5 Educational attainment?
2. What is the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar District in terms of;
 - 2.1 Differentiated Instruction;
 - 2.2 Active learning;

- 2.3 Technological Integration; and
- 2.4 Effective Communication?
- 3. Is there a significant difference in the teaching strategies when data are grouped according to;
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Civil status;
 - 3.4 Length of Service; and
 - 3.5 Educational attainment;

METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the research design and method used in this study. In more details, the researcher outlined in this chapter the research design, locale of the study, respondents of the study sampling technique, research instrument, data gathering procedure, validity and reliability, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Research Design was used in research to refer to the researcher's plan of how to proceed. This design allows data to be collected at a single point in time and can be used for a descriptive study as well as determination of relationship between variable.

1. The Socio- Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age, Gender, Civil status, Length of Service, Employment status
2. The Extent of teaching strategies for student's engagement and learning as assessed by teachers at Omar district in terms of Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, Effective Communication.
3. The Significant difference in the teaching strategies for engagement and learning when grouped according to socio- demographic profile of the respondents?
4. The Significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the teaching strategies for student's engagement and learning as assessed by teachers in Omar District?

The study were conducted among teachers in Omar district, Sulu. The respondents of this study were one hundred (100) selected teachers at Omar district, Sulu, was the main source of data which was quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet were the source of information that were used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research, the data from the respondents were collected through the use of questionnaires.

Research Locale

The study was conducted among teachers in Omar district School, Ministry of Basic Higher Technical Education (MBHTE), division-Sulu during the School year 2023-2024.

Respondents of The Study

The respondents of the study were One hundred (100) respondents of which all are Teachers from different schools in Omar district under Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE), division- Sulu during the School year 2023-2024.

Selected teachers were drawn to represent each of the school at Omar district, Division-Sulu. Table below shows the distribution of samples in this study.

Distribution of the Target Samples among Selected school.

Schools in Omar district	Number of Respondents
Sucuban Elementary School	10
Bandahala Elementary School	10
Angilan Elementary School	10
Kapual Elementary School	10
Imam Abdusali Elem. School	10
Andalan Elementary School	10
Huwit-Huwit Elementary School	10
Likubung Elementary School	10
Tanduh Panuan Elementary School	10
Kasulutan Elementary School	10
TOTAL	100

Sampling Design

In this study, the researcher used a purposive sampling, also known as judgmental selection or subjective sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

The researcher utilized purposively one hundred (100) respondents from Omar district. The use of purposive sampling study and help the study to meet its goals.

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument to be employed to gather data on the extent of teaching strategies for student's engagement and learning as assessed by teachers in Omar district, Sulu during the Academic year 2023-2024. In the context of the Extent of teaching strategies for student's engagement and learning as assessed by teachers at Omar district in terms of Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, Effective Communication.

The questionnaire was adapted and patterned from the study of Dr. Igbaria, et al, et.al, (2015), teaching strategies and their role on student's engagement in English.

This model encompasses the following teaching strategies;

- 1.1 Differentiated Instruction
- 2.2 Active learning
- 2.3 Technological Integration
- 2.4 Effective Communication

Research Instrument

The research instrument was utilized in this study consist of two parts. Part I of the questionnaire which focused on obtaining the demographic profile of the teacher respondents.

Part II focused towards obtaining data on the extent of Data to be obtained using this questionnaire was analysed through 5-point modified Likert scale such as 5=Strongly Agree (SA), 4=Agree (A), 3=Uncertain (U), 2=Disagree (D), 1=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedure were employed in the course of data gathering: A permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the office of the Dean of Graduates studies, Sulu state college through a formal letter and then a letter that addressed to the MBHTE, Division-Sulu unit head then, to the District Supervisor of Omar to make them aware about the purpose of conducting the study. The launching and administering, as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were conducted personally by the researcher. The researcher also ensures the confidentiality and anonymity of responses to encourage honest answers.

This chapter presents the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the findings based on the data collected for this study, which aimed to determine the teaching strategies for students' engagement and learning as assessed by teachers in Omar district, Sulu on fiscal year 2023. It examines the teacher-respondents' demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, civil status, length of service, and educational attainment; and the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. It also explores the differences and correlations among these variables based on the teacher-respondents' demographic profiles.

The following are the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of results according to the research questions and the data analysis methods:

Validity and Reliability

The instrument used in this research was adapted and patterned from the study of *Dr. Igbaria, et al, (2015) with the title "teaching startegies and their role on student's engagement in English*

It was a standardized research instrument with established validity and reliability. However, to suit its usability in the local setting, a slight modification were made and these were subjected to the perusal of at least two (2) experts from the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of Sulu state College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. To determine the Socio- Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age, Gender, Civil status, Length of Service, Employment status The statistical tools were used are Frequency and percentage.
2. To determine the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district in terms of Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, Effective Communication. The statistical tools were used are mean and standard deviation.

1. What is the Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 civil status, 1.4 length of service, and 1.5 educational attainment?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu in terms of age. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, the majority are between 26-35 years old who make up 49% (49). This is followed by those aged 36-45 years, below 25 years, and above 46 years, accounting for 25% (25), 22% (22), and 4% (4) respectively. This shows that majority of the teacher-respondents are in their early adulthood stage. This means that there is a difference of at least 24% between the other groups. This implies a highly skewed age distribution among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.1 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
25 years old and below	22	22%
26-35 years old	49	49%
36-45 years old	25	25%
46 years old and above	4	4%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu in terms of gender. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, it highly concentrated towards female teacher-respondents who make up 85% (86), while male teacher-respondents account for 15% (15). This means that there is a gender gap of 70% between the female and male groups. This implies a highly skewed gender distribution among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1. Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	15	15%
Female	85	85%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Civil Status

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu in terms of civil status. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, single and married have the same frequency, making up 47% (47) each. This is followed by those who are widowed and separated, accounting for 4% (4), and 2% (2) respectively. This shows that most of the teacher-respondents are either single or married. This means that there is a difference of at least 43% between the other groups. This implies a highly skewed civil status distribution among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.3 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of Civil Status.

Civil Status	Number of Respondents	Percent
Single	47	47%
Married	47	47%
Widowed	4	4%
Separated	2	2%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu in terms of length of service. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 5 years and below, and 6-10 years in service have the same frequency, making up 39% (39) each. This is followed those who have been employed for 11-20 years, and 21 years and above, accounting for 20% (20), and 2% (2) respectively. This means that most of the teacher-respondents have been employed for

either 5 years and below, or 6-10 years, with a gap of at least 19% between the other groups. This implies a highly skewed distribution of length of service among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.5 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

Length of Service	Number of Respondents	Percent
5 years and below	39	39%
6-10 years	39	39%
11-20 years	20	20%
21 years and above	2	2%
Total	100	100%

1.5 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 154 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents from different schools in Omar district, Sulu in terms of educational attainment. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, most have bachelor's degree, making up 90% (90). This is followed by those with master's unit, master's degree, and doctorate degree, accounting for 6% (6), 3% (3), and 1% (1) respectively. This shows that most of the teacher-respondents have bachelor's degree. This means that there is a difference of at least 84% between the other groups. This implies a highly skewed distribution of educational attainment among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.5 Teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of educational attainment.

Educational Attainment	Number of Respondents	Percent
Bachelor's degree	90	90%
Master's units	6	6%
Master's Degree	3	3%
Doctorate degree	1	1%
Total	100	100%

attainment.

2. What is the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of 2.1 Differentiated Instruction, 2.2 Active learning, 2.3 Technological Integration, and 2.4 Effective Communication?

2.1 In the context of Differentiated Instruction

Table 2.1 shows the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of differentiated instruction. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.436, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree". The total standard deviation is 0.40240, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in

their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents at Omar district, Sulu assessed the extent of differentiated instruction on teaching strategies with high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agreed that they use various assessment methods such as pre-assessment observations and student feedback to gather information about strength and weaknesses, interest, and prior knowledge, group the students based on their needs and abilities allowing them to work collaboratively, and employ a range of teaching methods, materials and resources to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences. Further, they strongly agree that they provide targeted interventions and accommodations for students with special needs or learning difficulties and modify the pace and level of challenge to meet individual student needs. The highest agreement is on providing targeted interventions and accommodations for students with special needs or learning difficulties, which indicates that the teachers are aware of and responsive to the diversity of their students. The lowest agreement is on using various assessment methods to gather information about students' strengths, weaknesses, interests, and prior knowledge, which suggests that there is room for improvement in this area.

Table 2.1 Extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of differentiated instruction.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I use various assessment methods such as pre-assessment observations and student feedback to gather information about strength and weaknesses, interest, and prior knowledge.	4.36	.503	Agree
2. I group the students based on their needs and abilities allowing them to work collaboratively.	4.37	.506	Agree
3. I employ a range of teaching methods, Materials and resources to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences.	4.44	.519	Agree
4. I modify the pace and level of challenge to meet individual student needs.	4.50	.541	Strongly Agree
5. I provide targeted interventions and accommodations for students with special needs or learning difficulties	4.51	.577	Strongly Agree
Total	4.4360	.40240	Agree

Legend: **4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)**, **3.50-4.49 = Agree (A)**, **2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M)**, **1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D)**, **1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)**

2.2 In the context of Active Learning

Table 2.2 shows the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of active learning. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.564, which indicates an overall rating of “Strongly Agree”. The total standard deviation is .43147, which indicates that there is less variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents at Omar

district, Sulu assessed the extent of active learning on teaching strategies with very high level.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents strongly agree that they encourage students to actively participate, asks questions and discuss concepts, encourage students to actively involve problem solving, group discussions and hands-on activities, promote deep learning by providing students with multiple opportunities to practice and reinforce their understanding of concepts, encourage students cooperation and teamwork, nurtures essential, interpersonal skills and prepares them for real -world environments, and empower student to take responsibility to their learning. The highest agreement is on encouraging students to actively participate, ask questions, and discuss concepts, which implies that the teachers recognize the importance of student engagement and dialogue in active learning. The lowest agreement is on promoting deep learning by providing students with multiple opportunities to practice and reinforce their understanding of concepts, which indicates that there is still room for improvement in this aspect of active learning.

Table 2.2 Extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of active learning.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I encourage students to actively participate, asks questions and discuss concepts.	4.61	.549	Strongly Agree
2. I encourage students to actively involve problem solving, group discussions and hands-on activities.	4.57	.573	Strongly Agree
3. I promote deep learning by providing students with multiple opportunities to practice and reinforce their understanding of concepts.	4.51	.541	Strongly Agree
4. I Encourage students' cooperation and teamwork, nurtures essential, interpersonal skills and prepares them for real -world environments.	4.60	.550	Strongly Agree
5. I empower student to take responsibility to their learning.	4.53	.559	Strongly Agree
Total	4.564	0.43147	Strongly Agree

Legend: **4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)**, **3.50-4.49 = Agree (A)**, **2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M)**, **1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D)**, **1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)**

2.3 In the context of Technological Integration

Table 2.3 shows the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of technological integration. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.0180, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree". The total standard deviation is .53718, which indicates that there is some variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents at Omar district, Sulu assessed the extent of technological integration on teaching strategies with high level.

The mean scores indicated that the teacher-respondents agreed that they help students to engage in technology like multimedia resources, etc., help the students are

well trained to use software and other platforms, help the students have a wide access to online research materials, e-books and digital libraries, help students collaborate and communicate in an online platform, and help the students adapt to digital age. The highest agreement is on helping students to engage in technology, which implies that the teachers recognize the importance of using multimedia resources and other technological tools to enhance student engagement and learning. The lowest agreement is on helping students to have a wide access to online research materials, which indicates that there might be some challenges or limitations in providing students with adequate and reliable online sources.

Table 2.3 Extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of technological integration.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I help students to engage in technology like multimedia resources, etc.	4.19	.615	Agree
2. I help the students are well trained to use software and other platforms.	4.01	.689	Agree
3. I help the students have a wide access to online research materials, e-books, and digital libraries.	3.87	.774	Agree
4. I help students collaborate and communicate in an online platform	3.94	.694	Agree
5. I help the students adapt to digital age.	4.08	.614	Agree
Total	4.0180	.53718	Agree

Legend: **4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA)**, **3.50-4.49 = Agree (A)**, **2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M)**, **1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D)**, **1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)**

2.4 In the context of Effective Communication

Table 2.4 shows the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of effective communication. The result shows that the total mean score is 4.3360, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is .54449, which indicates that there is some variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents at Omar district, Sulu assessed the extent of effective communication on teaching strategies with high level.

The mean scores indicated that the teacher-respondents agreed that use concise language to explain concepts, listen attentively to students’ questions, concerns, and ideas, maintain eye contact, and use appropriate facial expressions, use rephrasing or paraphrasing to students’ responses to help clarify misunderstanding and ensure comprehension, and I utilize visual aids such as charts, diagrams, videos, or slideshows. The highest agreement is on utilizing visual aids, which implies that the teachers recognize the importance of using charts, diagrams, videos, or slideshows to enhance student understanding and retention. The lowest agreement is on maintaining eye contact and facial expressions, which indicates that there might be some challenges or distractions in maintaining non-verbal communication.

Table 2.4 Extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu in terms of effective communication.

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. I use concise language to explain concepts.	4.35	.672	Agree
2. I listen attentively to students' questions, concerns, and ideas.	4.36	.689	Agree
3. I maintain eye contact and use appropriate facial expressions.	4.23	.664	Agree
4. I use rephrasing or paraphrasing to students' responses to help clarify misunderstanding and ensure comprehension.	4.31	.631	Agree
5. I utilize visual aids such as charts, diagrams, videos, or slideshows.	4.43	.640	Agree
Total	4.3360	.54449	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Moderate (M), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to 3.1 age, 3.2 gender, 3.3 civil status, 3.4 length of service, and 3.5 educational attainment??

3.1 In terms of Age

Table 3.1 presents the difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to age. The variables include Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for effective communication aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the assessments of teacher-respondents aged 25 years and below on the extent of these variables do not differ from those of teacher-respondents aged 26-35 years, 36-45 years, and 46 years and above, or vice versa. However, on the extent of effective communication aspect, the assessments of teacher-respondents aged 25 years and below differ from those aged 26-35 years, or vice versa, as shown in table 3.1.1. This implies that the teacher-respondents assess the extent of teaching strategies at Omar district, Sulu in the same way regardless of their age, except for effective communication aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to age." is accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Differentiated Instruction	Between Groups	.365	3	.122	.746	.527	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.665	96	.163			
	Total	16.030	99				
Active learning	Between Groups	1.328	3	.443	2.484	.065	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.103	96	.178			
	Total	18.430	99				
Technological Integration	Between Groups	.211	3	.070	.239	.869	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.356	96	.295			
	Total	28.568	99				
Effective Communication	Between Groups	2.543	3	.848	3.035*	.033	Significant
	Within Groups	26.808	96	.279			
	Total	29.350	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in the extent of effective communication when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

On Effective Communication: It shows that teacher-respondents aged 25 years and below obtained the mean difference of $-.37495^*$ with the Standard Error of .13562 and p-value of .034 over teacher-respondents aged 26-35 years which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.1.1 Multiple comparison of the extent teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu by age.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Effective Communication	25 years and below	26-35 years	$-.37495^*$.13562	.034
		36-45 years	-.33855	.15448	.133
		46 years and above	-.55455	.28724	.222

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.2 In terms of Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. The

variables include Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these variables does not affect the assessments of male and female teacher-respondents differently. This implies that the teacher-respondents assess the extent of teaching strategies at Omar district, Sulu in the same way regardless of their gender, except for work discipline. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.” is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Differentiated Instruction	Male	4.36	0.37947	-.08941	-.792	.430	Not Significant
	Female	4.4494	0.40697				
Active learning	Male	4.64	0.33123	.08941	.738	.462	Not Significant
	Female	4.5506	0.44711				
Technological Integration	Male	3.96	0.38693	-.06824	-.452	.652	Not Significant
	Female	4.0282	0.56074				
Effective Communication	Male	4.24	0.64675	-.11294	-0.739	0.462	Not Significant
	Female	4.3529	0.52703				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 In terms of Civil Status

Table 3.3 presents the difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status. The variables include Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for active learning aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the assessments of teacher-respondents who are single on the extent of these variables do not differ from those who are married, widowed, and separated, or vice versa. However, on the extent of active learning aspect, the assessments of teacher-respondents who are single differ from those who are married, or vice versa, as shown in table 3.4.1, This implies that the teacher-respondents assess the extent of teaching strategies at Omar district, Sulu, Sulu in the same way regardless of their civil status, except for active learning aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status.” is accepted.

Table 3.3 Difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Differentiated Instruction	Between Groups	.232	3	.077	.469	.704	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.799	96	.165			

	Total	16.030	99				
Active learning	Between Groups	1.495	3	.498	2.825*	.043	Significant
	Within Groups	16.936	96	.176			
	Total	18.430	99				
Technological Integration	Between Groups	.047	3	.016	.053	.984	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.520	96	.297			
	Total	28.568	99				
Effective Communication	Between Groups	.990	3	.330	1.117	.346	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.360	96	.295			
	Total	29.350	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to civil status have different levels of mean in the extent of active learning when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of civil status.

On Active Learning: It shows that single teacher-respondents obtained the mean difference of $-.24255^*$ with the Standard Error of $.08664$ and p-value of $.031$ over married teacher-respondents which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.3.1 Multiple comparison of the extent teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu. by civil status.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Active Learning	Single	Married	$-.24255^*$.08664	.031
		Widowed	.00106	.21876	1.000
		Separated	.05106	.30325	.998

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 3.4 presents the difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. The variables include Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for active learning aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the assessments of teacher-respondents who have been employed for 5 years and below on the extent of these variables do not differ from those who have been employed for 6-10 years, 11-20 years, and 21 years and above, or vice versa. However, on the extent of active learning aspect, the assessments of teacher-respondents who have been employed for 5 years and below differ from those who have been employed for 6-10 years, or vice versa, as shown in table 3.4.1. This implies that the teacher-

respondents assess the extent of teaching strategies at Omar district, Sulu in the same way regardless of their length of service, except for active learning aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service." is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Differentiated Instruction	Between Groups	.335	3	.112	.683	.565	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.695	96	.163			
	Total	16.030	99				
Active learning	Between Groups	2.048	3	.683	3.999*	.010	Significant
	Within Groups	16.383	96	.171			
	Total	18.430	99				
Technological Integration	Between Groups	.642	3	.214	.736	.533	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.926	96	.291			
	Total	28.568	99				
Effective Communication	Between Groups	.806	3	.269	.903	.443	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.545	96	.297			
	Total	29.350	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to length of service have different levels of mean in the extent of active learning when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

On Active Learning: It shows that teacher-respondents who have been employed for 5 years and below obtained the mean difference of $-.28205^*$ with the Standard Error of .09355 and p-value of .017 over teacher-respondents who have been employed for 6-10 years which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.4.1 Multiple comparison of the extent teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu. by civil status.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Active Learning	5 years and below	6-10 years	$-.28205^*$.09355	.017
		11-20 years	-.27026	.11362	.088
		21 years and above	-.51026	.29950	.327

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

3.5 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 3.5 presents the difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. The variables include Differentiated Instruction, Active learning, Technological Integration, and Effective Communication. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the assessments of teacher-respondents with bachelor's degree on the extent of these variables do not differ from those with master's unit, master's degree, and doctorate degree, or vice versa. This implies that the teacher-respondents assess the extent of teaching strategies at Omar district, Sulu in the same way regardless of their educational attainment. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment." is accepted.

Table 3.5 Difference on the extent of teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment.

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Differentiated Instruction	Between Groups	.514	3	.171	1.061	.369	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.516	96	.162			
	Total	16.030	99				
Active learning	Between Groups	.844	3	.281	1.536	.210	Significant
	Within Groups	17.586	96	.183			
	Total	18.430	99				
Technological Integration	Between Groups	1.209	3	.403	1.415	.243	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.358	96	.285			
	Total	28.568	99				
Effective Communication	Between Groups	.782	3	.261	.875	.457	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.569	96	.298			
	Total	29.350	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu?

Table 4 presents the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu. The table shows that the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05. Based on the table, the following interpretation are as follows:

- 1) Differentiated Instruction and Active Learning have a moderate positive correlation of .445*. This means that teacher-respondents who use more differentiated instruction tend to use more active learning strategies, and vice versa.
- 2) Differentiated Instruction and Technological Integration have a moderate positive correlation of .442*. This means that teacher-respondents who use more differentiated instruction tend to integrate more technology in their teaching, and vice versa.

- 3) Differentiated Instruction and Effective Communication have a moderate positive correlation of .418*. This means that teacher-respondents who use more differentiated instruction tend to communicate more effectively with their students, and vice versa.
- 4) Active Learning and Technological Integration have a low positive correlation of .235*. This means that teacher-respondents who use more active learning strategies tend to integrate more technology in their teaching, and vice versa. However, this correlation is weak and may not be very meaningful, and the effect size is small.
- 5) Active Learning and Effective Communication have a moderate positive correlation of .449*. This means that teacher-respondents who use more active learning strategies tend to communicate more effectively with their students, and vice versa.
- 6) Technological Integration and Effective Communication have a moderate positive correlation of .392*. This means that teacher-respondents who integrate more technology in their teaching tend to communicate more effectively with their students, and vice versa.

These correlations are statistically significant, meaning that it is not likely to be due to chance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu." is rejected.

Table 4. Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the teaching strategies as assessed by teachers at Omar district, Sulu.

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Differentiated Instruction	Active learning	.445*	.000	100	Moderate
	Technological Integration	.442*	.000	100	Moderate
	Effective Communication	.418*	.000	100	Moderate
Active learning	Technological Integration	.235*	.019	100	Low
	Effective Communication	.449*	.002	100	Moderate
Technological Integration	Effective Communication	.392*	.002	100	Moderate

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

1. To determine the significant difference in the teaching strategies when data are grouped according to socio- demographic profile of the respondents, the statistical tools were used are t-test for independent samples.

2. To determine the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under teaching strategies as assessed by teachers in Omar District, The statistical tools were used are Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r)

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to data collection, participants will be provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before their involvement in the research.

Participants' identities and sensitive information will be kept confidential throughout the study. Data will be securely stored and only accessed by the research ethics committee for analysis purposes.

Acknowledgements

Assalamual'ykum Waramatullahi Wal barakatuhu. It is a genuine pleasure to express my deep sense of thanks and gratitude to all those behind this success because of them I able to overcome many challenges and able to complete the requirements for Graduate Studies. So, I'm very proud that I reach This milestone of my life. This whole experienced would not be complete without giving thanks to these brilliant personalities to begin with:

DR. Charisma S. Ututalum, CESE, the Sulu State College President for her dynamic leadership in continuously strengthening the graduate program;

DR. Nelson U. Julhamid, Vice-President for academic affairs, for his keen interest in every stage of my research, his timely suggestion with kindness, enthusiasm and dynamism enable me to complete my thesis;

DR. Masnuna S. Asiri, the chairman of the defense panel, for her smooth voice in giving suggestion and correction of my works inspired me to do well with my research. Her kind help and enthusiasm really reflect her dedication towards her work;

DR. Anang Fatma T. Jawali, the adviser, her dedication and interest above all her overwhelming attitude really encourage me to work with my thesis. Her advice and guidance have help me to a very great extent to accomplish this task;

REFERENCES

- Alkash, K. A., & Al-Dersi, Z. E. (2013). Advantages of using PowerPoint presentation in EFL classroom & the status of its use in Sebha University. *IJ-ELTS*, 1(1)=pdf#page=4
- Costen, W. (2009). The value of staying connected with technology: An analysis exploring the impact of using a course management system on student learning. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport and Tourism Education*.
- Daugherty, C. (2014). The benefits of collaborative learning in the elementary Classroom. Sophia, *the St. Catherine University repository* <https://sophia.stkate.edu/maed/39>
- The benefits of collaborative learning in the elementary classroom. Sophia, *the St. Catherine University repository* <https://sophia.stkate.edu/maed/39>
- Gutek, G. L. (2013). *Philosophical, theoretical, and ideological perspectives on education* (2nd ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.